

Density and viscosity studies of binary mixtures of aniline with pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol and decan-1-ol at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

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From density and viscosity values of binary mixtures of aniline with pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol and decan-1-ol, measured at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K, excess molar volumes (V^E) and deviations in viscosity ($\Delta \ln \eta$) have been calculated. All mixtures show negative V^E values in a narrow region corresponding to low concentration of aniline and positive V^E values in a wide region corresponding to high concentration of aniline at all temperatures. $\Delta \ln \eta$ values for all mixtures are negative over the whole composition range at all temperatures.

The volumetric and viscometric properties of binary liquid mixtures containing alcohols as a function of molecular size, shape branching and molecular association of alcohols have been reported earlier from this laboratory¹. Since no reports are available of density and viscosity studies of aniline with alcohols (C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈, C₁₀), the effect of chain-length of alcohols on these properties of binary mixtures of aniline with alcohols (C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈, C₁₀) at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K is reported in the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

The density (ρ) and viscosity (η) values of binary mixtures of aniline with alcohols (C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈, C₁₀) at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are included in Table 1. The excess molar volumes (V^E) are calculated using equation,

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/\rho_{\text{mix}} - M_1x_1/\rho_1 - M_2x_2/\rho_2 \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{mix} is the density of the mixture and M_1, M_2, x_1, x_2 and ρ_1, ρ_2 are the molecular weight, mole fraction and density of pure components 1 and 2, respectively. The estimated uncertainties for V^E and $\Delta \ln \eta$ are $\pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $\pm 0.005 \text{ mPa s}$, respectively.

Several empirical equations have been proposed to correlate the viscosity of liquid mixtures which generally require adjustable parameters². Bloodfield and Dewan³ developed a theoretical relation to compute the $\Delta \ln \eta$ term without any adjustable parameters. The commonly used equation to predict the deviation in logarithmic viscosity, $\Delta \ln \eta$ is⁴

$$\Delta \ln \eta = \ln \eta_{\text{mix}} - x_1 \ln \eta_1 - x_2 \ln \eta_2 \quad (2)$$

where η_{mix} is viscosity of mixture and x_1, x_2 and η_1, η_2 are the mole fraction and viscosity of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

The variation of V^E and $\Delta \ln \eta$ with mole fraction of aniline (x_1) for all systems studied at 298.15 K are depicted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Similar plots are obtained at

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes (V^E) at 298.15 K for x_1 aniline + $(1-x_1)$ alkanols : (○) pentan-1-ol, (⊕) hexan-1-ol, (●) heptan-1-ol, (⊖) octan-1-ol, (⊙) decan-1-ol.

Note

other temperatures. From Fig. 1, we see that the sign of V^E value changes in unsymmetrical way with the change of mole fraction of aniline in the mixture. The unsymmetrical S-shaped curve of V^E vs x_1 (aniline) appears primarily due to steric factors arising from a change in the proportion of different geometric forms of aniline molecules with a change in its mole fraction. Similar unsymmetrical change of V^E has been reported for various binary mixtures⁵.

Fig. 2 includes plots of $\Delta \ln \eta$ vs x_1 at 298.15 K. The $\Delta \ln \eta$ values are negative over entire composition range of mixtures. In the present study, negative V^E values are obtained in alcohol-rich regions and positive in aniline-rich regions of binary mixtures. The negative V^E values may be ascribed to the interstitial accomodation of aniline molecules into the H-bonded aggregates of alcohols in alcohol-rich regions which outweighs the positive V^E owing to physical interactions and breaking up of alcohol clusters in the presence of aniline molecules. Positive V^E and negative $\Delta \ln \eta$ suggest that the dispersion forces prevail between aniline and alcohol molecules. The mechanism of the intermolecu-

Fig. 2. $\Delta \ln \eta$ values at 298.15 K for x_1 aniline + $(1-x_1)$ alkanols. (○) pentan-1-ol (◻) hexan-1-ol, (◻) heptan-1-ol, (◻) octan-1-ol, (◻) decan-1-ol.

Table 1. Density and viscosity of aniline with alcohols as function of mole fraction of aniline (x_1) at different temperatures

x_1	Density/(g cm ⁻³)				Viscosity/(mPa s)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
	Aniline + pentan-1-ol							
0.0000	0.8104	0.8066	0.8029	0.7991	3.420	2.859	2.582	2.251
0.0950	0.8197	0.8255	0.8213	0.8173	3.067	2.579	2.338	2.047
0.1900	0.8437	0.8392	0.8348	0.8305	2.848	2.383	2.167	1.904
0.2886	0.8580	0.8535	0.8491	0.8449	2.734	2.287	2.075	1.821
0.3869	0.8737	0.8693	0.8650	0.8608	2.682	2.244	2.031	1.785
0.4863	0.8910	0.8867	0.8824	0.8781	2.654	2.213	2.003	1.755
0.5868	0.9105	0.9062	0.9018	0.8976	2.686	2.239	2.023	1.774
0.7499	0.9470	0.9426	0.9380	0.9337	2.850	2.374	2.149	1.887
0.7911	0.9571	0.9524	0.9478	0.9436	2.923	2.433	2.208	1.942
0.8948	0.9849	0.9801	0.9752	0.9708	3.258	2.691	2.434	2.132
1.0000	1.0167	1.0123	1.0078	1.0037	3.717	3.049	2.740	2.381
	Aniline + hexan-1-ol							
0.0000	0.8156	0.8119	0.8084	0.8047	4.533	3.702	3.266	2.891
0.1087	0.8318	0.8320	0.8279	0.8235	3.954	3.254	2.903	2.572
0.2152	0.8458	0.8460	0.8420	0.8379	3.500	2.901	2.596	2.309
0.3199	0.8604	0.8602	0.8564	0.8521	3.257	2.693	2.403	2.139
0.4225	0.8764	0.8756	0.8716	0.8676	3.122	2.570	2.294	2.039
0.5231	0.8948	0.8935	0.8894	0.8853	3.021	2.495	2.231	1.978
0.6220	0.9145	0.9128	0.9087	0.9046	3.001	2.478	2.221	1.966
0.7135	0.9352	0.9329	0.9286	0.9245	3.003	2.486	2.234	1.968
0.8145	0.9617	0.9585	0.9541	0.9499	3.084	2.549	2.304	2.024
0.9081	0.9898	0.9857	0.9812	0.9769	3.267	2.705	2.456	2.152
1.0000	1.0167	1.0123	1.0078	1.0037	3.717	3.049	2.740	2.381

Aniline + heptan-1-ol								
0.0000	0.8162	0.8125	0.8087	0.8050	5.858	4.772	3.913	3.229
0.1218	0.8332	0.8295	0.8258	0.8221	4.919	4.050	3.409	2.869
0.2376	0.8500	0.8462	0.8424	0.8387	4.362	3.595	3.051	2.579
0.3485	0.8674	0.8636	0.8598	0.8560	4.004	3.304	2.830	2.403
0.4536	0.8854	0.8815	0.8776	0.8738	3.753	3.092	2.670	2.280
0.5550	0.9041	0.9002	0.8964	0.8926	3.540	2.919	2.542	2.178
0.6469	0.9228	0.9188	0.9149	0.9110	3.412	2.818	2.467	2.123
0.7444	0.9451	0.9411	0.9370	0.9331	3.312	2.732	2.419	2.088
0.8331	0.9677	0.9636	0.9594	0.9554	3.301	2.720	2.428	2.112
1.0000	1.0167	1.0123	1.0078	1.0036	3.717	3.049	2.740	2.381
Aniline + octan-1-ol								
0.0000	0.8206	0.8169	0.8133	0.8098	7.632	6.051	5.277	4.478
0.1345	0.8370	0.8332	0.8295	0.8260	6.049	4.894	4.324	3.725
0.2592	0.8536	0.8497	0.8459	0.8423	5.137	4.163	3.684	3.174
0.3747	0.8708	0.8668	0.8629	0.8592	4.593	3.740	3.325	2.864
0.4824	0.8886	0.8846	0.8806	0.8768	4.163	3.405	3.027	2.617
0.5830	0.9072	0.9030	0.8990	0.8951	3.845	3.140	2.807	2.435
0.6771	0.9265	0.9223	0.9182	0.9142	3.614	2.965	2.655	2.314
0.7654	0.9473	0.9430	0.9388	0.9348	3.478	2.865	2.579	2.257
0.8483	0.9693	0.9650	0.9606	0.9565	3.393	2.814	2.546	2.234
0.9264	0.9925	0.9881	0.9837	0.9794	3.460	2.874	2.590	2.263
1.0000	1.0167	1.0123	1.0078	1.0036	3.717	3.049	2.740	2.381
Aniline + decan-1-ol								
0.0000	0.8245	0.8208	0.8171	0.8135	11.487	9.260	7.517	6.143
0.1592	0.8411	0.8376	0.8341	0.8307	9.093	7.271	5.936	4.853
0.2985	0.8573	0.8537	0.8501	0.8466	7.445	5.956	4.909	4.023
0.4218	0.8740	0.8704	0.8667	0.8632	6.252	5.015	4.179	3.449
0.5306	0.8912	0.8875	0.8837	0.8801	5.404	4.343	3.655	3.021
0.6285	0.9090	0.9052	0.9014	0.8977	4.763	3.827	3.248	2.697
0.7184	0.9279	0.9240	0.9201	0.9164	4.250	3.419	2.933	2.447
0.8000	0.9485	0.9445	0.9404	0.9367	3.963	3.201	2.766	2.321
0.8602	0.9660	0.9619	0.9579	0.9541	3.798	3.072	2.683	2.262
0.9384	0.9926	0.9884	0.9841	0.9802	3.681	2.977	2.638	2.262
1.0000	1.0167	1.0123	1.0078	1.0037	3.717	3.049	2.740	2.381

lar interaction between aniline and alcohols can be explained as follows⁶. The dipoles in aniline and alcohol arise due to difference in electronegativities of nitrogen, oxygen and hydrogen. They are in the order, oxygen > nitrogen > hydrogen. Hence dipolar molecules are pictured as

There are three possibilities of dipole-interactions, (i) link-

age between $\text{N}^{\delta-}$ of aniline with $\text{H}^{\delta+}$ of alcohol, alcohol being proton donor, (ii) linkage between $\text{O}^{\delta-}$ of alcohol with $\text{H}^{\delta+}$ of aniline, here aniline acts as proton donor, and (iii) linkage between $\text{O}^{\delta-}$ of alcohol with $\text{N}^{\delta-}$ of aniline, alcohol being proton donor.

The observed V^E and $\Delta \ln \eta$ in the present investigation may be a result of the above three possibilities, and which of the possibilities prevails, is decided by the steric factors arising due to change of concentration of different geometric forms of aniline molecules. The positive V^E and negative $\Delta \ln \eta$ will correspond to the third possibility, resulting

Table 2. Comparison of experimental densities and viscosities of pure liquids with literature values at 298.15 K

Liquid	Density/(g cm ⁻³)		Viscosity/(mPa s)	
	Exptl.	Lit.	Experimental	Literature
Pentan-1-ol	0.8104	0.8107 ^a	3.420	3.510 ^a
Hexan-1-ol	0.8156	0.8160 ^a	4.533	4.574 ^b
Heptan-1-ol	0.8162	0.8185 ^c	5.858	5.937 ^b
Octan-1-ol	0.8206	0.8212 ^a	7.632	7.633 ^d
Decan-1-ol	0.8245	0.8254 ^e	11.487	11.567 ^b
Aniline	1.0167	1.0175 ^d	3.717	3.770 ^d

^aRef. 7, ^bP. S. Nikam, T. R. Mahale and M. Hasan, 1998. ^cRef. 8. ^dRef. 9. ^eRef. 10.

in the predominance of dispersive forces between aniline and alcohol molecules.

Experimental

Alcohols (C₅-C₁₀, Merck-Schuchardt, purity >99 mol %) were dried by refluxing over fused calcium oxide for 3–4 h and subsequently fractionally distilled two or three times. Aniline (s.d. Fine chemicals, purity >99.5 %) was used as obtained. The purity of solvents after purification was ascertained by GLC and also by comparing their densities and viscosities with the corresponding literature values at 298.15 K (Table 2). Aniline and alcohols were mixed in a stoppered glass bottle by mass with a precision of ±0.01 mg. Densities and viscosities of all degassed mixtures were measured using 15 cm³ bicapillary pycnometer and suspended level Ubbelohde viscometers, respectively, calibrated with conductivity water (~10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) as reported earlier¹, with accuracies of ±1 × 10⁻⁴ g cm⁻³ and ±0.001 mPa s, respectively.

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